

Deliverable 3.2

Complete chemical composition and bioactivity profiles of all extracts

Version 3.0

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WP 3
Deliverable 3.2
Lead Beneficiary: AAU
Call Identifier: HORIZON-CL6-2022-FARM2FORK-01
Grant Agreement No. 101084651
Dissemination Level: Public

IGNITION – Improving **Green** Innovation for the blue revolu**TION**: new tools and opportunities for a more sustainable animal farming is funded by the European Union (Grant Agreement: 101084651)

Executive Summary

This report focuses on the extraction and characterization of bioactive phytochemicals from halophytes, which are naturally rich in phenols, flavonoids, antioxidants, and other beneficial compounds. The fractionated biomass of *Salicornia ramosissima* and *Suaeda maritima* was investigated for nutrients, phenols, flavonoids, antioxidants, and tannins, as well as for enzyme inhibition and cytotoxicity. Comparative analysis of halophyte fibre extracts revealed higher extractive content and increased enzyme inhibition but lower total phenolic content (TPC) in *S. ramosissima* compared to *S. maritima*. The water extracts of *S. maritima* yielded 36.60 ± 3.06 mg gallic acid equivalent (GAE)/g extractives dry matter (DM), whereas *S. ramosissima* exhibited 18.98 ± 1.54 mg GAE/g extractives DM, nearly half. Cytotoxicity, on the other hand, varied with the type of extract and cell lines used, making final comparisons inconclusive. Additionally, extracts of *S. maritima* were subjected to untargeted metabolites analysis, confirming richness in active plant metabolites such as quercetin, isorhamnetin, and many others. The chemical composition analysis of green juice and fractionated fibres revealed that the juices from each halophyte plant are rich in sugars, protein, and salts > 55% w/w. Additionally, the juiced fibres consist mainly of sugars > 52% w/w and Klason lignin > 12% w/w.

Subsequently, investigation of the total phenols content, antioxidant activity, and hydroxycinnamic acids content in *S. ramosissima*, *S. maritima*, and *Suaeda vera total plant biomass* showed that *S. ramosissima* has higher total phenolic content (TPC), while *S. maritima* has higher antioxidant activities and total content of hydroxycinnamic acids (HCA), which is highly desirable. Conversely, *S. vera* has significantly inferior TPC, antioxidant activity, and HCA compared to the other halophytes, resulting in its exclusion from further experimental work. The total flavonoid compounds (TFC) was 7.00, 5.31, and 1.56 mg of GAE/g halophyte DM for *S. ramosissima*, *S. maritima*, and *S. vera*, respectively. Furthermore, the total antioxidant activity was 1.24, 0.64, and 0.37 mg of GAE/g halophyte DM for *S. ramosissima*, *S. maritima*, and *S. vera*, respectively.

S. ramosissima was prioritised in further research due to its higher availability. The cascade extraction process demonstrated high reproducibility, with subcritical water extraction (SWE) showing better results in flavonoids and phenols extraction. However, ultrasound pre-treatment yielded inconclusive results, except for increased flavonoids recovery. The optimal temperature of SWE for TFC was 140°C, resulting in a 2.9 mg of quercetin equivalent (QE)/g

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halophyte DM and a continuous increase in TPC up to 150°C, reaching over 200 mg of GAE/g extractives DM.

In conclusion, this study identifies *S. maritima* and *S. ramosissima* as promising sources of bioactive compounds and provides valuable insights into extraction methods and conditions. To maximise the potential of halophytes in various industrial and medicinal applications, further research focusing on optimization and understanding of mechanisms is required.

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

AChE	acetylcholinesterase
BuChE	butyrylcholinesterase
CE	catechin equivalent
CEL	dry extract
DAD	diode array detector
DM	Dry matter
DMEM	Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium
FAME	fatty acid methyl ester
FRAP	ferric ion reducing antioxidant power
GAE	gallic acid equivalent
HCA	Hydroxycinnamic acids
HMF	Hydroxymethylfurfural
NPCF	nitrogen-to-protein conversion factor
PUFA	polyunsaturated fatty acids
QE	quercetin equivalent
S/SE	Soxhlet extraction
SWE	Subcritical water extraction
TCT	Total condensed tannins
TFC	total flavonoid compounds
TPC	total phenolic content
TPTZ	tripyridyltriazine

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1. Introduction

Due to their large diversity and natural adaptability, halophytes are emerging supercrops. Thanks to their high saline tolerance, reaching 200 mM NaCl or more, their habitats spread from equatorial deserts to arctic oceans, where they make up about 1% of the flora [1]. Their main benefit lies in their suitability for cultivation in marginal lands, thus avoiding competition with traditional crops [2]. Currently, halophytes are getting a lot of interest from the food, health, and cosmetic industries due to their richness in bioactive compounds such as phenols, carotenoids, vitamins, and others [3, 4]. Research has shown that they can also produce significant amounts of other bioactive compounds, including antioxidants, [5], giving halophytes the potential to be used in novel nutraceuticals, pharmaceuticals, and high-quality animal feed [6, 7].

Herbs and their extracts have shown promising results as fish feed additives. Studies have demonstrated that these extracts can positively affect growth performance, activate immune cells, boost phagocytosis, and increase the secretion of inflammatory markers, thereby enhancing the fish's defences against several pathogens and environmental stressors [8, 9]. Halophytes and their products have been previously reported to be excellent functional ingredients for fish diets. Marçal et al. [10] demonstrated that including *Salicornia ramosissima* in conventional fish feed for European seabass increased antioxidant and genoprotective activity in the fish tissue. Similarly, Barreto et al. [11] reported that adding *S. ramosissima* into European seabass feed had health-promoting effects without detriment to growth performance. Furthermore, Machado and colleagues [12] showed that incorporating *S. ramosissima* in feed improved European seabass's inflammatory response against *Photobacterium damsela piscicida*. Moreover, Belal and Al-Dosari [13] showed *Salicornia bigelovii* can partially replace fish meal in Nile tilapia feed. However, the effect of halophyte extracts on fish health and growth is yet to be investigated.

Moreover, due to their ability to tolerate and accumulate salt, they can also be used in phytoremediation of salt-affected soils [14, 15]. In addition to saline agriculture, early studies indicate they might be useful for CO₂ capture [16]. Overall, commercialising and cultivating salt-tolerant halophytes could significantly improve the quality of areas affected by soil salinity, prevent further soil degradation, and make use of their natural phytoremediation capabilities. However, halophyte species have a limited season when they can be explored for food, as the plant becomes increasingly lignified as it matures, making it inedible. Furthermore, the high salt content in halophytes limits their direct use for animal feed, composting, incineration, and soil enhancement. For this reason, mature halophyte biomass is often categorised as agricultural waste [17]. Upcycling of non-food grade plants or their parts based on green

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biorefinery includes fractionation via screw-press into a liquid fraction, referred to as green juice, and a fibre fraction, referred to as press cake [18, 19]. For halophyte-based biorefinery, preference lies in the extraction of high-value bioactive compounds from whole or juiced plant fibres [20, 21].

As part of IGNITION, *S. ramosissima* and *Suaeda maritima* were selected for the extraction, identification, quantification, purification, and analysis of their bioactive compounds. However, *S. maritima* biomass collected was insufficient, firstly due to reduced growth in South Denmark in 2023, possibly as the result of competition from invasive species; and secondly due to a misidentification of *S. maritima* purchased from a private source, later identified as *Suaeda vera* through genotyping. Consequently, due to the limited availability, *S. maritima* was only used in characterization studies and not for extraction and purification optimization, as initially planned. To avoid this hindrance in the future, *S. maritima* will be harvested from multiple sources to ensure availability for further work. As a bonus, *S. vera* was investigated for its bioactive extracts yield. In summary, this report will examine the chemical and bioactive compound compositions of three halophyte plants, *S. ramosissima*, *S. maritima*, and *S. vera*, alongside optimising the bioactive extraction and purification from *S. ramosissima* (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Overview of performed experimental and analytical work: 1) Analysis of fractionated halophyte biomass, 2) Analysis of whole lignified halophyte biomass, 3) Optimization of extraction and purification on whole *S. ramosissima*

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2. Materials and methods

2.1. Biomass pre-processing

For green biomass characterization, *S. ramosissima* was obtained from Riasearch in September 2023, and *S. maritima* was gathered from Mandø, Denmark, in October 2022. The *S. ramosissima* biomass was fractionated on the 12th of October 2023 at the demonstration-scale grass processing facility, in Aarhus University, in Foulum, Denmark, and *S. maritima* was fractionated with a lab-scale juicer. The green juice was stored at -20°C until use, and juiced halophyte fibres were dried at 60°C and stored at room temperature.

In the case of the whole plant analysis, the same *S. ramosissima* and *S. maritima* specimens used for juicing were employed; however, no fractionation step was undertaken. *S. vera* was obtained in November 2023 from Seawater Solutions, UK, then dried at 60 °C and stored at room temperature. Dried lignified whole *S. ramosissima* was utilised for the extractions. *S. ramosissima* was cultivated at the Riasearch facility in Portugal and harvested at full maturity. The fully lignified *S. ramosissima* was shredded at a Nordic Engineering pilot scale washer/shredder, and washed to remove the salts that were not bound in the plant tissue. After washing, the biomass was drained using a 2 mm sieve and dried in an oven at 60 °C for 48 hours. The dried biomass was carefully weighed, packed into plastic bags, and stored at room temperature.

2.2. Dry matter and ash analysis

To ensure comparable results, dry matter (DM) content was calculated. Beakers and triplicate samples of approximately 10 g were weighed. The beakers, including biomass, were placed in an oven at 105°C for 24 hours, after which they were weighted. The DM content of one sample was calculated as:

$$DM\% = \frac{m_{after} - m_{beaker}}{m_{before} - m_{beaker}} \cdot 100$$

Where m_{after} is the mass of the beaker and the biomass after evaporation, m_{before} is the mass of the beaker and the biomass before evaporation, and m_{beaker} is the mass of the respective beaker.

Clean crucibles were ashed in a furnace at 550°C for 5 hours, and once the furnace had cooled below 80°C (approximately 18 hours), compressed filtered air was used to remove any

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fine particles. Crucibles were kept in a desiccator before use. Approximately 2.5 g of biomass was placed in three weighted crucibles each. The crucibles containing the biomass were placed in the furnace and ashed at 550 °C for 5 hours. After the furnace cooled down, the samples were removed, and the mass was noted. The ash content, as percentage of the DM, was calculated:

$$Ash_{DM\%} = \frac{m_{after} - m_{crucible}}{m_{before} - m_{crucible}} \frac{1}{DM\%} \cdot 100$$

Where m_{after} is the mass of the crucible and the biomass after ashing, m_{before} is the mass of the crucible and the biomass before ashing, and $m_{crucible}$ is the mass of the crucible.

2.3. CNHS analysis and crude protein approximation

A CHNS elemental analyser (Pekin Elmer 2400 series CHNS/O) was used to analyse the carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen, and sulphur content of the dried samples. For the analysis, 2-10 mg of each sample was weighed in small tin capsules. The principle of the elemental analyser involves combustion at approximately 1000 °C, converting carbon to carbon dioxide, hydrogen to water, nitrogen to nitrogen gas or nitrogen oxides, and sulphur to sulphur dioxide. The combustion products are then detected by the CHNS elemental analyser.

The protein content was calculated based on the nitrogen content using a nitrogen-to-protein conversion factor (NPCF) of 6.25, assuming that all proteins contain 16% (w/w) nitrogen. This value, sourced from the literature, is an approximation, but is widely accepted and commonly used [22, 23].

The formula used for the nitrogen-to-protein conversion is:

$$N \cdot NPCF = P$$

Where N = nitrogen content % (w/w) in the dried sample

NPCF = mass ratio of nitrogen to protein = 6.25

P = Protein content % (w/w) in the dried sample.

2.4. Carbohydrate determination

The NREL protocol was used for the analysis of sugars in green halophyte juice [24]. Samples were filtered with a 0.22 µm syringe filters into vials for HPLC analysis (Bio-Rad Aminex HPX-87H Column, Bio-Rad Laboratories Inc.), using a H₂SO₄ mobile phase (0.005 M) and RID

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(Refractive Index Detector) for sugar (glucose, cellobiose, xylose, and arabinose) and ethanol. Lactic acid was analysed, using a H_3PO_4 mobile phase (0.2 v/v %) and DAD (Diode Array Detection).

The method to detect carbohydrates in fibres was based on the NREL protocol [25]. Produced acidic hydrolysates and supernatants were filtered with a 0.22 μm syringe filters into vials for HPLC analysis (Bio-Rad Aminex HPX-87H Column, Rio-Rad Laboratories Inc.), using H_2SO_4 mobile phase (0.005 M) and refractive index detector for sugar (glucose, cellobiose, xylose, and arabinose). Sugar content was calculated as a percentage of DM [26]. A hydration factor of 0.9 was used to estimate glucan content from glucose concentration, while a hydration factor of 0.88 was applied to estimate xylan and arabinan from pentoses.

2.5. Lipid extraction and lipid profile analysis

The Soxhlet extraction (S/SE) method was used for the lipid extraction [27]. The lipid composition was determined using the fatty acid methyl ester (FAME) analysis [27]. Triglycerides, phospholipids, and free fatty acids were converted to FAME and analysed with GC-MS.

2.6. Lab-scale Soxhlet extraction

The plant extracts were prepared with a conventional laboratory-scale Soxhlet system. S/SE is a commonly used, reliable, and replicable method for solid-liquid extraction, and the principle of continuous evaporation, simultaneous condensation, and cyclic siphoning of extract allows the production of concentrated extract without mass transfer limitations (Figure 2). The extraction chamber has a volume of 100 mL, and 250 mL of solvent was used for the extraction. The extraction time was 8 to 10 hours for water extracts, and 6 to 8 hours for ethanol and n-hexane extracts, and the obtained amount of extractive material was determined using a protocol by NREL [28]. These extracts were used for phytochemicals and bioactivities analysis

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Figure 2: Lab-scale Soxhlet extraction

After extraction, the extracts were frozen at $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. To recover extractives, the frozen extracts were freeze-dried (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Freeze-drying for recovery of extracts

2.7. Subcritical water extraction and extract preparation

Subcritical water extraction (SWE) was performed in a 3-L working volume reactor (Nordic Engineering, Roskilde, Denmark). Setting the solid loading at 5% w/v, 35 g of dried *S. ramosissima* and 700 mL of water were added to the reactor. The paddle mixer was set at 70 % to enhance heat and mass transfer during the heating, extraction, and cooling. Based on the experimental setup, the temperature and time varied between 100-160 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 15 minutes to an hour, respectively. After the cooling step, the reactor was stopped when the temperature

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reached 60 °C, and the extract was filtered with a 2 mm pore-size sieve. The clean fibres were squeezed and dried in a heating cabinet (Memmert, model 30-1060) at 60 °C for 24 hours. The extract was acidified with HCl 32% v/v to set pH to 2 ± 0.1 . This step is intended to stabilise the bioactive phenolics. Then, the extract was centrifuged at 3500 rpm for 15 minutes. After separating from the supernatant, the pellet was dried in a heating cabinet (Binder, model ED 115) at 105 °C for 24 hours for further total DM analysis. The supernatant was filtered through a DWK Life Sciences DURAN™ Filter Disc Sintered Glass, Porosity 1, and then through a DWK Life Sciences DURAN™ Filter Disc Sintered Glass, Porosity 3, in Figure 4. The filter cake was discarded and assumed negligible in mass balance calculations. The filtrate was stored at -20 °C until use.

Figure 4: Extract filtration

2.8. Subcritical water extraction pilot-scale

The SWE was conducted on *S. ramosissima* in the 100 L pilot-scale reactor. The reactor was filled with 55 L DM water and preheated up to 70 °C. 1180 g of *S. ramosissima* was then added to the reactor, and the final temperature was set to 130 °C. After reaching the temperature set point, the SWE was performed for 30 minutes. Mixing was applied during the preheating, extraction, and cooling to maximize heat and mass transfer. The mixture was then cooled down to 60 °C before being transferred into the next tank. The extract passed through a membrane and microfilter in the next tank and collected in the collection tank. The extract was sampled and stored at -20 °C until use. The extracted fibres were squeezed and dried in a heating cabinet (Memmert, model 30-1060) at 60 °C for 24 hours.

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2.9. Soxhlet extraction pilot-scale

For S/SE in the pilot scale plant, 1180 g of *S. ramosissima* was divided into three metal baskets. Then, 83 L of DM water preheated to 90 °C was poured over the baskets, initiating the Soxhlet process. The residence time for the Soxhlet was 30 minutes. The SE parameters are shown in Table 8. This cycle was repeated four times, equivalent to 8 hours of Soxhlet in the lab scale apparatus. After each cycle, the extract underwent filtration through a membrane and microfilter before being collected in the tank. To start the next cycle, 83 L of preheated DM water was poured over the baskets, followed by repeating all the steps above. The extract from each cycle was sampled and stored at -20 °C until use.

2.10. Total contents of phenolic compounds

The total phenolic content (TPC) was determined using gallic acid as a standard according to the Folin-Ciocalteu method [29]. This method is widely applied in the determination of the TPC of plant-derived samples. The Folin-Ciocalteu reaction is based on electron transfer, which measures the reductive capacity of any substance (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Calibration curve in total phenolic content assay

The total flavonoid content (TFC) was also estimated in the dried extract at a concentration of 10 mg/mL, using the method developed by Pirbalouti [30] adapted to 96-well plates (Figure 6). Aliquots of 50 μ L of the samples were mixed with 50 μ L of 2% aluminium chloride in MeOH solution. The plates were incubated for 10 minutes at RT and read at 405 nm (EZ Read 400, Biochrom, Cambridge, United Kingdom). Results were expressed as the amount of quercetin equivalent (QE) per gram of dried extract.

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Figure 6: Calibration curve for total flavonoid content assay

Total condensed tannins (TCT) of dried extracts at 10 mg/mL were determined using a method described by Li et al. [31] using p-dimethylaminocinnamaldehyde hydrochloric acid (DMACA-HCl). 10 μ L of extracts were mixed with 200 μ L of 1% DMACA in MeOH and 100 μ L of 37% HCl. Plates were incubated for 15 minutes at RT and read at 640 nm (EZ Read 400, Biochrom, Cambridge, United Kingdom) (Figure 7). Results were expressed as the amount of catechin equivalent (CE) per gram of dried extract.

Figure 7: Calibration curve for total condensed tannins assay

2.11. Untargeted analysis of selected metabolites

Water and ethanol extracts, dissolved in their respective solvents at a concentration of 2 mg/mL, were subjected to analysis using HPLC coupled with high-resolution mass spectrometry. The separation process utilised ultra-high performance liquid chromatography

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(U-HPLC) with an UltiMate 3000 system from Thermo Scientific, employing an RP-18 column (Accucore, 2.1 x 100 mm, 2.6 μm particle size). The mobile phase consisted of water and acetonitrile, both supplemented with 0.1% formic acid. The solvent gradient began with 100% water for 2 minutes, followed by a linear increase of acetonitrile to 30% over 30 minutes and to 100% over 16 minutes. Finally, the mobile phase was returned to 100% water for an additional 5 minutes. The flow rate within the system was maintained at 0.3 mL/minute, with a sample injection volume of 10 μL . Mass analysis was conducted using a mass spectrometer (Orbitrap Elite, Thermo Scientific) equipped with heated electrospray ionisation. The instrument parameters included spray voltages of 3.7 kV (positive mode) and 4.0 kV (negative mode), sheath gas and auxiliary gas set at 40 arbitrary units and 10 arbitrary units, respectively, and heater and capillary temperatures maintained at 300 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 350 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, respectively. Compounds were detected within the mass range of 100 – 1000 m/z , and fragmentation spectra were acquired using a data-dependent mode with dynamic exclusion. The obtained data were analysed using (Compound Discoverer 3.3 software from Thermo Scientific). Compounds were annotated utilising various databases, including mzCloud, Arita Lab 6549 Flavonoid Structure Database, EFS HRAM Compound Database, Endogenous Metabolites database of 4400 compounds, LipidMaps Structure database, and Natural Products Atlas 2020-06.

2.12. Antioxidant activity

Ferric ion reducing antioxidant power (FRAP) assay was performed to evaluate the antioxidant activity of extracts [32]. The method is based on the reduction at low pH of a colourless ferric complex (Fe^{3+} -tripyridyltriazine (TPTZ) to a blue-coloured ferrous complex (Fe^{2+} -TPTZ) by the action of electron-donating antioxidants. The reduction was monitored by measuring the change of absorbance at a wavelength of 593 nm with a spectrophotometer (Genesys 150, Thermo Scientific, Waltham, USA).

The FRAP assay was performed with 25 mg/DM of the freeze-dried sample dissolved in 25 mL water. No replicates were taken for each sample. Calibration curves were compared with previous calibration curves to ensure consistency (Figure 8). FRAP reagent was prepared directly before use, by mixing one volume of 31 mg of TPTZ in a 10 mL aqueous solution of HCl (40 mM) with one volume of 54 mg $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 10 mL of acetate buffer (pH 3.6). This mixture was kept at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Simultaneously, the calibration curve using an aqueous solution of FeSO_4 (0.1-1 mM) was prepared. Immediately, 60 μL of blank FeSO_4 standards and diluted extracts were mixed with 2 mL of FRAP reagent and the solution was kept at room temperature for exactly 4 minutes. Then the solution was transferred to a UV/Vis cell and the absorbance

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was measured at 593 nm. The antioxidant activity of the extracts is given as millimoles of Fe (II) equivalent/g of extract.

Figure 8: Calibration curve in FRAP assay

An alternative approach to determine the antioxidant activity is the 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) assay. The DPPH radical has a strong purple colour in the solution (Figure 9). In the presence of compounds capable of either transferring an electron or donating hydrogen, the DPPH becomes pale yellow, and the disappearance of the purple colour can be measured spectrophotometrically. The change in DPPH absorbance after the addition of test material is used as an index of the antioxidant capacity of the material [33]. Calibration curves were compared with previous calibration curves to ensure consistency. 5 mg of DPPH was dissolved in 25 mL of MeOH. A calibration curve was made by different gallic acid solutions from 1 to 10 mg/L. 750 μ L of each gallic acid solution and 750 μ L of the sample were distributed in individual 1.5 ml spectrophotometer cuvettes. 750 μ L of the DPPH solution was added. Samples were measured at 515 nm on a spectrophotometer (Cary WinUV, Agilent, Santa Clara, USA) and were performed after 30 minutes of dark incubation at room temperature. The results were obtained by considering the IC₅₀ of the DPPH and were given as milligram gallic acid equivalent (GAE) per gram of dry extract (CEL) or directly calculated to g GAE per kg DM (AAU).

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Figure 9: Complete microplate in DPPH assay

2.13. Enzyme inhibition

For *in vitro* enzyme inhibition activity, the extracts were tested against enzymes associated with type 2 diabetes mellitus (α -amylase and α -glucosidase), obesity and acne (lipase), hyperpigmentation (tyrosinase), and neurodegenerative diseases, such as Alzheimer's disease (acetylcholinesterase and butyrylcholinesterase (AChE and BuChE)) [34–38]. Detailed protocols have been previously described [21, 39]. The results are expressed as percentages of inhibition at 10 mg/mL concentration, based on the negative control. For comparison, the results were benchmarked against commercial medicinal compounds such as galantamine, arbutin, acarbose, and orlistat.

2.14. Cytotoxicity

The cytotoxicity of the extracts to mammalian cells was tested using three cell lines provided by the Centre of Marine Sciences of the University of Algarve: S17 (healthy mice murine bone marrow stromal cells), HepG2 (human hepatocarcinoma), and RAW 264.7 (mice leukemic macrophage). Cells were maintained in a Dulbecco's Modified Eagle culture medium (DMEM) supplemented with 10% inactivated foetal bovine serum, 1% 2 mM L-glutamine, and 1% 50 U/mL penicillin/50 μ g/mL streptomycin at 37°C humidified atmosphere with 5% CO₂. Cells were passed when 70 – 80% confluence was reached, and a minimum of two cell division cycles with minimal observed morphological modifications were passed before using the cells in assays. The cell viability was tested using a colorimetric assay with 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-

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2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide (MTT) as described in [40]. Cells were seeded to 96-well plates with a density of 5×10^3 cells/well (S17 and HepG2) and 10×10^3 cells/well (RAW 264.7) and incubated for 24 h. When cells were attached to the bottom of the wells, extracts were applied with a concentration of 200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, and plates were further incubated for 72 hours. Afterwards, 20 μL of 5 mg/mL MTT in phosphate-buffered saline was added, and plates were incubated for 2 hours. Viable cells converted MTT to purple crystals, which were then dissolved into 150 μL DMSO. Absorbance was read at 590 nm (Biotek Synergy 4, Biochrom), and results were expressed as a percentage of cell viability based on the negative control cells with no added extract. Extracts exhibiting cell viability below 75% were considered cytotoxic at the tested concentration.

2.15. Hydroxycinnamic acids assay

To prepare the samples for analysis on HPLC, the crude liquid extract was acidified with 70% phosphoric acid to pH 2, approximately 2 drops per 50 mL, and filtered through a 0.45 μm syringe filter into an HPLC vial. HCAs are a sub-class of chemicals in the group of phenolic acids and some derivatives of HCAs (chlorogenic acid) or hydroxybenzoic acids (gallic acid, vanillic acid). The HPLC system used was an Agilent 1260 Infinity HPLC system consisting of a quaternary pump, a degasser, an auto-sampler, and a diode array detector (DAD). The separation was achieved with the help of an Agilent Zorbax Eclipse plus C18 (4.6 \times 250 mm, 5 μm) column. The column was maintained at 30°C. A post-run to clean the column was done for 5 minutes after the program. The flow was 0.7 mL/minute and the detection wavelength was 254 nm. The gradient system consists of solvent A (Milli Q water, with 0.2% Phosphoric acid) solvent B (Acetonitrile), and solvent C (MeOH). Different gradient programs were evaluated internally. The most efficient gradient program is shown in Table 1:

Table 1: Solvent system gradient of elution for polyphenols method on HPLC

Time [min]	Solvent A [%]	Solvent B [%]		Solvent C [%]	
	Ultra-pure water acidified with 0.2 % H_3PO_4	Acetonitrile grade	HPLC	MeOH grade	HPLC
0	96	2		2	
45	70	15		15	
55	50	25		25	
60	40	30		30	
65	96	2		2	

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As the HPLC analysis yields a value in mg/L, it was converted into mg/kg DM by applying the following equation:

$$m_{HCA \text{ per kg DM}} = \frac{C_{HCA} \cdot V_{H_2O, tot}}{m_{sample}} \cdot \frac{1}{DM\%}$$

Where $m_{HCA \text{ per kg DM}}$ is the HCA content in mg/kg DM, C_{HCA} is the HCA concentration in mg/L of extract. Due to inconsistencies in the results, not all HCA analyses have been included in the report.

3. Results

The chemical analysis and bioactivities were investigated in three halophytic plants: *S. ramosissima*, *S. maritima*, and *S. vera*. In the case of *S. ramosissima* and *S. maritima*, two types of biomass were analysed: green biomass and lignified biomass. For *S. vera* only lignified biomass was characterized.

Firstly, structural compounds such as sugars, lipids, and crude protein were analysed, followed by the determination of total phenolic compounds (TPC), total flavonoid compounds (TFC), and total condensed tannin (TCT) and cytotoxicity in water and ethanol extractives in green biomass of *S. ramosissima* and *S. maritima*.

Secondly, the full plant biomass of *S. ramosissima*, *S. maritima*, and *S. vera* were investigated for bioactivities.

Thirdly, *S. ramosissima*, due to its abundance, was used for novel extraction approaches that were tested to increase the yield of bioactives.

3.1. Analysis of fractionated biomass of *S. ramosissima* and *S. maritima*

S. ramosissima was fractionated using a pilot-scale juicer, whereas *S. maritima* was fractionated with lab-scale equipment. After fractionation, *S. ramosissima* green juice and fibre residue fractions constituted 66.7% and 33.3% of the total fresh biomass. In *S. maritima*, juice constituted 57.1% and fibre fraction 42.1% of the fresh biomass.

3.1.1. Proximate chemical composition of *S. ramosissima* and *S. maritima*

Green juice of *S. maritima* was rich in lipids, sugars, crude protein, and ash, which, to a large extent, represent salt (Figure 10). The high salt content may negatively affect the application of the juice in fish feed. The fibre residue was 63% w/w carbohydrates, making it a prospective

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second-generation feedstock for biorefinery. Furthermore, remaining nutrients, lipids, and crude protein cover 15.9% w/w in fibre residue on a dry basis, making it a relatively nutritious feedstock for animals.

Figure 10: Composition of fractionated *S. maritima*. Note that the cumulative mass balance of fibre residue exceeds 100 %.

Figure 11 shows that the green juice of *S. ramosissima* is abundant in sugars and crude protein. However, nearly two-thirds of dried biomass is ash, suggesting a considerably high salt content. The fibre residue is based on 52% w/w carbohydrates, 10% w/w of crude protein, and 3 % w/w of lipids, considerably less than *S. maritima* fibres. Overall, both plants are nutritious and could directly serve as feed ingredients or precursors for animal feed production.

Figure 11: Composition of fractionated *S. ramosissima*

Moreover, the fatty acid profile of *S. maritima* was investigated, as shown in Table 2. Based on the results, it can be concluded that lipids from *S. maritima* are predominantly based on 85-90% w/w C18 fatty acids followed by 10-14% w/w C16 fatty acids. C18-2 and C18-3 fatty acids, corresponding to 69-73 % w/w of present lipids, are also known as polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA), which are recognized as desirable dietary fats in fish feed [41].

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Table 2: Fatty acid profile of *S. maritima* fractions

Fatty acid	<i>Suaeda maritima</i> juice [% FA/total FA]	<i>Suaeda maritima</i> fibre residue [% FA/total FA]
C12	n.d.	0.14 ± 0.06
C14	n.d.	0.17 ± 0.04
C16	13.92 ± 0.39	9.93 ± 0.21
C16-1	n.d.	0.28 ± 0.01
C18	4.63 ± 0.35	1.39 ± 0.04
C18-1	12.51 ± 0.67	15.08 ± 0.65
C18-2	63.26 ± 0.25	67.21 ± 0.92
C18-3	5.67 ± 0.22	5.85 ± 0.09

3.1.2. Water and ethanol extractives

In both species, extractive material constituted approximately 25% of the fibre DM, as shown in Figure 12. The majority of the extractives were removed with water. The amount of ethanol extractives was higher in *S. maritima*, likely due to the late harvest stage and the presence of seeds.

Hydrothermal pre-treatment was performed in an autoclave for extractives-free lignocellulosic fibres at 120°C for 30 minutes. Afterwards, sugar degradation products were tested from pre-treatment liquid, and enzymatic saccharification was performed for pre-treated fibres with 6% enzyme loading and 10% DM loading. An additional 5% of the fibre DM was extracted from the pre-treatment liquid. Furfural and Hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF) were not detected from the pre-treatment liquid samples. However, only very low sugar recoveries (<10% w/w) for all measured sugars (glucose, xylose, and arabinose) were measured after enzymatic saccharification.

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Figure 12: The content of extractive material in *S. ramosissima* and *S. maritima* dry matter (DM).

3.1.3. Bioactive compounds in extracts

The contents of total phenolic compounds (TPC), TFC, and total condensed tannin (TCT) were determined from the extracts by the Folin-Ciocalteu, aluminium chloride, and DMACA-HCl methods, respectively. The results are described as amounts of GAE, QE, and CE, respectively, in extract DM based on the calibration curve. There were issues carrying out the total flavonoids assay, which should be repeated due to the suboptimal quality of the calibration curve ($R^2 = 0.93$). Antioxidant activity, determined at ferric reducing antioxidant power (FRAP), was measured at the concentration of 10 mg/mL. The results in Table 3 demonstrate that *S. maritima* has more TPC in water extract compared to *S. ramosissima*. Furthermore, water extract resulted in the highest TPC for *S. maritima*, which is desirable. Other analyses did not show considerable variation between the two plants.

Table 3: Concentration of bioactive compounds and antioxidant activity of extracts

Extract	TPC [mgGAE/gDM]	TFC [mgQE/gDM]	TCT [mgCE/gDM]	FRAP [%]
<i>Salicornia ramosissima</i>				
Water extract	18.98 ± 1.54	Not detected	1.89 ± 1.44	54.90 ± 2.40
Ethanol extract	18.85 ± 4.00	N/A	N/A	N/A
Pre-treatment liquid	39.44 ± 6.94	Not detected	Not detected	45.12 ± 7.01
<i>Suaeda maritima</i>				
Water extract	36.60 ± 3.06	Not detected	1.29 ± 0.28	54.68 ± 2.23

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Ethanol extract	26.75 ± 6.03	N/A	N/A	N/A
Pre-treatment liquid	23.87 ± 3.11	Not detected	4.55 ± 1.24	38.91 ± 6.15

3.1.4. Enzyme inhibition activity

The capability to inhibit enzymes related to various chronic diseases was determined for extracts at a concentration of 10 mg/mL. Acetylcholinesterase and butyrylcholinesterase (AChE and BuChE) are linked to neurodegenerative diseases, α -amylase and α -glucosidase to diabetes, and tyrosinase for hyperpigmentation. Results in Table 4 were benchmarked against medicinal products currently on the market, and galantamine and arbutin were tested at 1 mg/mL, whereas acarbose was tested at the same concentration as samples (10 mg/mL). The ethanol extract from *S. maritima* was very rich in lipids (see Figure 10), which caused precipitation in the assays, and it was not possible to reliably read the results of α -glucosidase and tyrosinase inhibition assays. It was not possible to determine α -glucosidase and tyrosinase activities in *S. ramosissima* ethanol extract due to the insufficient volume of available extract.

Table 4: Enzyme inhibition [%] activity of extracts at 10 mg/mL concentration.

Extract	AChE	BuChE	α -Amylase	α -Glucosidase	Tyrosinase
<i>Salicornia ramosissima</i>					
Water extract	22.53 ± 6.69	No activity	3.40 ± 1.90	20.77 ± 2.46	9.85 ± 2.82
Ethanol extract	66.54 ± 12.44	38.81 ± 8.38	24.36 ± 4.06	N/A	N/A
Pre-treatment liquid	23.81 ± 5.20	No activity	No activity	3.83 ± 1.28	10.56 ± 1.47
<i>Suaeda maritima</i>					
Water extract	4.74 ± 1.91	No activity	No activity	8.83 ± 0.28	7.18 ± 1.61
Ethanol extract	41.26 ± 7.68	No activity	21.97 ± 1.04	N/A	N/A
Pre-treatment liquid	9.24 ± 5.46	No activity	3.88 ± 2.07	9.14 ± 1.15	13.70 ± 4.51
Reference compounds					
Galantamine	93.05 ± 4.81	48.96 ± 3.84	N/A	N/A	N/A
Acarbose	N/A	N/A	83.41 ± 4.29	83.36 ± 0.71	N/A
Arbutin	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	58.03 ± 2.27

AChE: Acetylcholinesterase; BuChE: butyrylcholinesterase

3.1.5. Cytotoxicity of halophyte extracts

Cytotoxicity of the extracts was tested using the following mammalian cell lines: S17 (healthy mice murine bone marrow stromal cells), HepG2 (human hepatocarcinoma), and RAW 264.7

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(mice leukemic macrophage). The cell viability was tested with a 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide (MTT) assay. Samples were tested at 200 µg/mL concentration, and cell viability < 70% was considered cytotoxic. None of the extracts fulfilled the criterion of IC50 values below 30 µg/mL (Table 5), set by the American National Cancer Institute for raw extracts relevant to be used in anti-tumoral applications [42].

Table 5: Cell viability [%] after applying the extracts at 200 ug/mL concentrations. * Cell viability at 100 ug/mL.

Extract	S17	HepG2	RAW 264.7
<i>Salicornia ramosissima</i>			
Water extract	91.67 ± 9.54	96.87 ± 3.75	90.55 ± 6.94
Ethanol extract	83.39 ± 4.50	83.54 ± 7.72	13.95 ± 1.71 79.52 ± 6.46*
Pre-treatment liquid	106.44±5.00	N/A	62.05 ± 6.17 68.54 ± 6.97*
<i>Suaeda maritima</i>			
Water extract	108.19±7.80	91.09 ± 9.88	68.68 ± 3.15 73.75 ± 5.33*
Ethanol extract	94.54±12.07	97.71 ± 4.67	67.10 ± 6.60 119.19 ± 13.62*
Pre-treatment liquid	105-51±9.25	89.69 ± 9.97	71.54 ± 7.55

S17: healthy mice murine bone marrow stromal cells; HepG2: human hepatocarcinoma; RAW 264.7: mice leukemic macrophage

3.1.6. Plant metabolites analysis

S. maritima extract were dissolved into water or ethanol with a 2 mg/mL concentration and analysed using UHPLC coupled with high-resolution mass spectrometry. The mass spectrometer used heated electrospray as an ionisation source, and both negative and positive ionisation was performed. Data were analysed using software (Compound Discoverer 3.3, Thermo Scientific), and compounds annotated using mzCloud, Arita Lab 6549 Flavonoid Structure Database, EFS HRAM Compound Database, Endogenous Metabolites database of 4400 compounds, LipidMaps Structure database 2021-09-13, and Natural Products Atlas 2020-06. For the annotated compounds, the deviation of the measured and theoretical mass (Δmass) was $-5.0 \leq \Delta\text{mass} \leq 5.0$, the mzCloud Best Match score was $\geq 85\%$, and it had matches in one or several databases. Qualitative detection of secondary metabolites in the

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ethanol extract of *S. maritima* (Table 6) was performed to confirm the presence of potent compounds such as Isorhamnetin, Quercetin, Quercetin-3 β -D-glucoside, Isokaempferide, and Isoquercetin. The same was done for *S. maritima* water extracts, to confirm the presence of compounds of high interest (Table 7).

Table 6: Compounds annotated from *S. maritima* ethanol extract

Compound name	m/z [M+H] ⁺ +1	m/z [M-H] ⁻ -1	RT [minute]
1-Linoleoyl glycerol	355.28342	N/A	25.404
6-O-Methylscutellarin	477.10254	N/A	15.657
Isokaempferide	301.07074	N/A	19.833
Isorhamnetin	317.06542	N/A	15.237
Linoleoyl ethanolamide	324.28915	N/A	28.244
Oleic acid	283.26303	N/A	31.883
Oleoyl ethanolamide	326.30536	N/A	30.218
Palmitoyl ethanolamide	300.28921	N/A	30.623
Pinolenic acid	279.23209	N/A	26.437
Quercetin	303.04963	N/A	14.223
α -Eleostearic acid	279.23153	N/A	25.564
α -Linolenic acid	279.23136	N/A	28.997
α -Linolenoyl ethanolamide	322.27338	N/A	26.832
4-Hydroxybenzoic acid	N/A	137.02438	7.973
Apigenin	N/A	269.04469	19.543
Azelaic acid	N/A	187.09713	14.628
Linoleic Acid	N/A	279.23218	25.406
Luteolin	N/A	285.03966	17.938
Palmitic Acid	N/A	255.23232	26.366
Quercetin-3 β -D-glucoside	N/A	463.08698	14.203
Suberic acid	N/A	173.08177	12.425
α -Eleostearic acid	N/A	277.21664	28.96
γ -Linolenic acid	N/A	277.21661	24.442
trans-Petroselinic acid	N/A	281.2478	31.817

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Table 7: Compounds annotated from *S. maritima* water extract

Compound name	m/z [M-H] ⁺ 1	m/z [M-H] ⁻ 1	RT [minute]
4,5-Dicaffeoylquinic acid	N/A	515.1177	14.588
4-Anisic acid	N/A	151.03999	7.597
Astragalin	N/A	447.0921	15.081
Azelaic acid	N/A	187.09718	14.659
Chlorogenic acid	N/A	353.08658	10.653
D-(-)-Quinic acid	N/A	191.05558	10.627
Ferulic acid	N/A	193.05021	13.354
Gentisic acid	N/A	153.01921	5.962
Glycitein	N/A	283.06039	18.723
Glycyl-L-leucine	N/A	187.10835	4.14
Isovanillic acid	N/A	167.03486	7.81
Luteolin	N/A	285.03993	16.779
N-Feruloyloctopamine	N/A	328.11807	14.09
Neochlorogenic acid	N/A	353.0867	8.642
Quercetin-3 β -D-glucoside	N/A	463.08724	14.233
Suberic acid	N/A	173.08176	12.427
6-O-Methylscutellarin	477.10227	N/A	15.557
Isorhamnetin-3-O-galactoside	479.11829	N/A	15.271
Kaempferol 3-O-galactoside	449.10767	N/A	15.087
Riboflavin	377.14524	N/A	11.879
Nobiletin	403.13826	N/A	22.341
Isorhamnetin	317.0655	N/A	15.27
Isokaempferide	301.07023	N/A	19.866
Scopoletin	193.04958	N/A	13.158
Quercetin	303.04956	N/A	14.233
Kaempferol	287.05495	N/A	15.097
Pinolenic acid	279.23163	N/A	19.759

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3.2. Analysis of full plant biomass of *S. ramosissima*, *S. maritima*, and *S. vera*

S. ramosissima was provided by Riasearch in September 2023, and *S. maritima* was gathered from Mandø, Denmark, in October 2022. *S. vera* was obtained from Seawater Solutions (UK) in November 2023, and was originally presented as *S. maritima*. However, genotyping confirmed that it was *S. vera*.

3.2.1. Bioactive compounds analysis of *S. ramosissima*, *S. maritima*, and *S. vera*

The analysis of TPC and antioxidant activity, depicted in Figure 13, shows that *S. ramosissima* as a whole plant has higher bioactivities when compared with *S. maritima* and *S. vera*. Water and ethanol extractions of *S. vera* resulted in 13.5% w/w of extractives per dried plant biomass, with ethanol extraction of 5.9% w/w extractives per dried plant biomass. Overall, it can be suggested that *S. vera* is poor in bioactive compounds compared to other halophyte species studied.

Figure 13: TPC and antioxidant activity of halophyte plants water extracts

3.2.2. Metabolites of *S. ramosissima*, *S. maritima*, and *S. vera*

Hydroxycinnamic acids (HCA) are phenolic phytochemicals commonly found in plants. They are considered to have medical properties, mainly antioxidants, anti-tumour, antimicrobial, and antidiabetic activities [43, 44]. Figure 14 shows that *S. maritima* has a higher concentration of HCA compared with *S. ramosissima*. Moreover, the extract of *S. vera* seems to be considerably low in HCA except for cinnamic acid.

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Figure 14: HCA analysis in halophyte water extracts via HPLC

Moreover, extracts of *S. vera* were analysed with UHPLC coupled with high-resolution mass spectrometry, showing that extracts are rich in Quercetin, Ferulic acid, Nicotiflorin, Isorhamnetin, Isorhamnetin-3-gly, and Quercetrin-3-gly and possess small amounts of Naringenin, Pratensein, Chlorogenic acid, and Scopoletin. However, in comparison with extracts from other halophytes, both the type and quantity of bioactives are considerably lower in *S. vera*, rendering it less desirable for extract production. Additionally, water and ethanol extracts of *S. vera* were analysed on LC-MS (Liquid chromatography–mass spectrometry) (Figure 15). Results show that ethanol extract is significantly richer in all measured metabolites.

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Figure 15: Approximated metabolites in *S. vera* based on LC-MS

3.3. Extraction optimization on *S. ramosissima*

S. ramosissima was readily accessible, for that reason, the decision was made to focus on optimising and scaling up the process specifically for this halophyte. The limitation of *S. maritima* biomass led to the postponement of extraction optimization. Additionally, *S. vera* was excluded from subsequent experimental trials due to its low yield of desired bioactive compounds.

3.3.1. Description of the process

The cascade extraction (Figure 16) process consists of the following units: a shredder, wash, and press, a subcritical reactor with a loop-to-ultrasound cell, a percolation reactor, and a liquid storage tank with an ultrafiltration unit for concentrating compounds and recycling water. The demonstration-scale plant's capacity, during proof-of-concept, was 100 L of solvent, with a maximum biomass packing capacity of 5000 g of biomass per batch.

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Figure 16: Picture of the multistep cascade extraction.

3.3.2. Biomass

Fully lignified *S. ramosissima* was harvested in Murtosa, Portugal (at Riasearch) and shipped to AAU. The biomass was shredded using the 2-EM01/Biomass Cutting Mill CM2500 from Nordic Engineering to a particle size between 2 and 5 mm, washed three times with tap water and drained using a press. The biomass was then dried in a heating cabinet for 48 hours at 60°C before being transferred to the extraction units.

3.3.3. Cascade extraction trials

To show the effect of the cascade process, several extractions were run on the demonstration plant. Table 8 shows biomass loading, total volume, process temperature, and residence time for the different units. Table 9 gives an overview and explanation of the trials run.

Table 8: Biomass loading and process parameters for the different extraction unit operations.

Extraction	Biomass loading (w/V) %	Total volume (L)	Temp/ time
Soxhlet (4 runs)	1.42	83 (x 4)	100 °C/30 minutes.
Subcritical	1.82 - 2.14	55 - 65	130 °C/ 30 minutes
Ultrasound (2 separate containers)	59	10	20 °C/ 60 minutes

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Table 9: Explanation for the different trials, which were run as part of the reference and cascade extraction trials.

Extraction method ID	
SWE1	Subcritical Water Extraction (SWE) 1 (for reference and replicability of the plant)
SWE2	Subcritical Water Extraction (SWE) 2 (for reference and replicability of the plant)
S	Soxhlet (S) (for reference)
C1-C8	Cascade 1-8

3.3.4. Soxhlet cycle optimization trials

Besides the reference and cascade extractions, optimisation trials were also performed to determine the number of Soxhlet cycles that should be included in the cascade. One to four Soxhlet cycles were run for Soxhlet alone and for Soxhlet as part of a cascade. An overview of the trials carried out in this study is shown in Table 10.

Table 10: Explanation for the different trials carried out to optimise the number of Soxhlet cycles in the cascade.

Extraction method ID	
S1-S4	Four Soxhlet cycles run on raw biomass
US1-US4	Four Soxhlet cycles run on ultrasound-pre-treated fibres
C1-C8	Four extraction cycles with various extraction combinations of ultrasound, soxhlet, and SWE

3.3.5. Cascade extractions

The reference and cascade extractions were compared in terms of the total extractives fraction obtained, total polyphenolic content, total flavonoid content, and antioxidant capacity in the produced extracts (Figure 17).

Two subcritical water extractions were performed to investigate the process replicability, as this is a high-temperature pressurised process and one of the more complex steps in the cascade. While a slightly higher total amount of extract was produced in SWE1 than in SWE2, the content of total phenolics and antioxidant capacity was very similar in the two experiments (Figure 17). In general, the two trials were found to be replicable.

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For the reference trials, SWE and S/SE performed similarly, but with a higher amount of total phenolics and flavonoids being extracted in SWE.

The effect of ultrasound as a pre-treatment in the reference extraction with *S. ramosissima* was minimal, as also observed in the lab-scale trials. Ultrasound was used initially as a pre-treatment of the raw biomass, as a first step in the cascade. However, ultrasound is currently being used as part of the cascade, as it was determined that the cascade yields a higher total content of flavonoids when this is applied as a pre-treatment.

In the future, it should also be investigated if ultrasound can have an effect on recalcitrant fibre residues, in a more advanced step in the cascade. Also, detailed analysis of individual compounds might reveal specific compounds that will react to ultrasounds. In the future, applying ultrasound in the cascade may reveal importance when utilising their halophyte species biomasses.

At these proof-of-concept trials, the positive effects of the cascade extractions are clear. In all combinations C1-C6 of ultrasound, SWE, and S/SE, a significantly higher amount of total extractives was achieved, resulting in higher total phenolics, flavonoids, and antioxidant capacity.

Figure 17: Total amount of extractives fraction obtained in the reference and cascade extractions as well as the total amount of phenolics, flavonoids, and antioxidant capacity of the obtained extracts.

3.3.6. Analysis of multistep Soxhlet cycle

Based on the results, SWE, followed by S/SE, is a very promising cascade in the extraction of polyphenols and flavonoids from *S. ramosissima*. The number of cycles of Soxhlet needed to

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achieve the optimal result was investigated. Figure 18 shows that the first cycle of extraction results in the highest recovery of bioactives while ultrasound as a pre-treatment did not have a positive effect on extraction. Techno-economical assessments should be performed to fully assess the benefit of multiple-cycle extraction.

Figure 18: The total amount of extractives fraction, the total amount of phenolics, flavonoids, and antioxidant capacity obtained after one to four cycles of Soxhlet on raw fibres (S1-S4), fibres after subcritical water extraction (SWE+S), ultrasound pre-treated fibres (US), and fibres after the ultrasound and subcritical water extraction cascade.

3.3.7. Temperature optimization for the Subcritical Water Extraction step

Even though the SWE step had previously been optimised at lab scale (1-5 litre), a set of trials were performed to examine the optimal temperature for the SWE in this new demonstration-scale plant. Temperatures of 100, 110, 120, 130, 140, and 150°C were tested with a residence time of one hour. It was observed that TFC only peaks at 140°C and drops at 150°C (Figure 19). On the other hand, TPC increased from 120°C to 150°C of extraction temperature. Overall, a compromise between extraction yield and degradation of bioactive compounds should be sought to achieve the highest yield.

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Figure 19: TFC and TPC after the varying temperature of the subcritical water extraction step

4. Discussion and conclusion

A initial comparative analysis of fractionated biomass from *S. ramosissima* and *S. maritima* yielded varied results. The water extract from *S. ramosissima* contained a higher quantity of extractives. Additionally, *S. ramosissima* showed increased enzyme inhibition but also higher cytotoxicity compared to *S. maritima*. Furthermore, upon investigating the whole plant biomass of *S. ramosissima*, *S. maritima*, and *S. vera*, it was found that *S. ramosissima* has higher TPC yield. However, *S. maritima* exhibited higher antioxidant activities and a total content of HCA, which is highly desirable. *S. vera*, having significantly lower TPC, antioxidant activity, and HCA, compared to the other two halophytes, should be excluded from further experimental work. Based on the results, determining the ideal candidate between *S. ramosissima* and *S. maritima*, for extraction optimization and scale-up, remains inconclusive.

Given the higher availability of *S. ramosissima* biomass, it was decided to prioritise this halophyte in further research. For that reason, the cascade extraction process was tested on this halophyte. The optimization trials showed that extractions on *S. ramosissima* is highly reproducible. Between tested individual extraction methods, SWE was shown to be superior for TFC and TPC. No difference was observed for total extractives and total antioxidant capacity between S/SE and SWE. The combination of two extractions significantly increased the yields of bioactives.

Analysis of multiple Soxhlet cycles revealed that the initial extraction cycle yielded the majority of bioactive compounds, with subsequent cycles resulting in significantly diminished yields. Additionally, ultrasound was found to have no effect on the extraction of bioactive compounds, except for increased flavonoids recovery. Temperature optimization for the SWE step showed 140°C to be optimal for TPC, with further increases in temperature having detrimental effects, probably due to phenolic degradation at high temperatures [45]. Conversely, TFC showed a

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continuous increase with temperature up to 150°C. To fully assess the effect of the temperature on TFC, higher temperatures should be investigated.

In conclusion, this study provides valuable insights into the composition of *S. ramosissima*, *S. maritima*, and *S. vera* and the extraction of bioactive compounds from halophytes, particularly *S. ramosissima*. These findings contribute to advancing the field of halophyte-based bioactive compound extraction and have implications for various industrial and medicinal applications. These processes could, however, gain from further optimisation. In the scope of the IGNITION project, the results contribute significantly to the formulation of new functional feeds and feed additives, which will subsequently be tested in *in vitro* and *in vivo* fish trials, thus advancing sustainable and circular aquaculture.

5. Ongoing and future work

Currently, the most abundant extracts of *S. ramosissima* are being analysed in terms of TPC total flavonoid content, and antioxidant capacity after optimising the cascade extraction process. Simultaneously, new approaches and optimizations for the extraction of bioactives from *S. ramosissima* are being explored. An updated version of this document, with new results and more well-defined conclusions, would be desirable.

In the upcoming summer of 2024, the top priority will be to gather sufficient quantity of *S. maritima* for characterization and optimization trials. As new biomass is gathered over the next few months, it will be processed and analysed. The updated and final report will be available by spring 2025.

6. References

1. Flowers TJ, Colmer TD (2008) Salinity tolerance in halophytes. *New Phytol* 179:945–963. <https://doi.org/10.1111/J.1469-8137.2008.02531.X>
2. Accogli R, Tomaselli V, Drenzo P, et al (2023) Edible Halophytes and Halo-Tolerant Species in Apulia Region (Southeastern Italy): Biogeography, Traditional Food Use and Potential Sustainable Crops. *Plants* 2023, Vol 12, Page 549 12:549. <https://doi.org/10.3390/PLANTS12030549>
3. Hulkko LSS, Chaturvedi T, Thomsen MH (2022) Extraction and Quantification of Chlorophylls, Carotenoids, Phenolic Compounds, and Vitamins from Halophyte

PROFILES OF ALL EXTRACTS

- Biomasses. Applied Sciences 2022, Vol 12, Page 840 12:840. <https://doi.org/10.3390/APP12020840>
4. Giordano R, Saii Z, Fredsgaard M, et al (2021) Pharmacological Insights into Halophyte Bioactive Extract Action on Anti-Inflammatory, Pain Relief and Antibiotics-Type Mechanisms. Molecules 2021, Vol 26, Page 3140 26:3140. <https://doi.org/10.3390/MOLECULES26113140>
 5. Ksouri R, Megdiche W, Falleh H, et al (2008) Influence of biological, environmental and technical factors on phenolic content and antioxidant activities of Tunisian halophytes. C R Biol 331:865–873. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CRVI.2008.07.024>
 6. Ksouri R, Ksouri WM, Jallali I, et al (2012) Medicinal halophytes: potent source of health promoting biomolecules with medical, nutraceutical and food applications. Crit Rev Biotechnol 32:289–326. <https://doi.org/10.3109/07388551.2011.630647>
 7. Chaturvedi T, Christiansen AHC, Gołębiewska I, Thomsen MH (2021) *Salicornia* Species: Current Status and Future Potential. Future of Sustainable Agriculture in Saline Environments 461–482. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003112327-31>
 8. Ahmadifar E, Fallah HP, Yousefi M, et al (2021) The Gene Regulatory Roles of Herbal Extracts on the Growth, Immune System, and Reproduction of Fish. Animals 2021, Vol 11, Page 2167 11:2167. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ANI11082167>
 9. Tadese DA, Song C, Sun C, et al (2022) The role of currently used medicinal plants in aquaculture and their action mechanisms: A review. Rev Aquac 14:816–847. <https://doi.org/10.1111/RAQ.12626>
 10. Marçal R, Sousa P, Marques A, et al (2023) Exploring the Antioxidant and Genoprotective Potential of *Salicornia ramosissima* Incorporation in the Diet of the European Seabass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*). Animals 2024, Vol 14, Page 93 14:93. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ANI14010093>
 11. Barreto A, Couto A, Jerónimo D, et al (2024) *Salicornia ramosissima* Biomass as a Partial Replacement of Wheat Meal in Diets for Juvenile European Seabass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*). Animals 2024, Vol 14, Page 614 14:614. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ANI14040614>
 12. Machado M, Cruz F, Cunha A, et al (2024) Dietary *Salicornia ramosissima* improves the European seabass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*) inflammatory response against *Photobacterium damsela* piscicida. Front Immunol 15:1342144. <https://doi.org/10.3389/FIMMU.2024.1342144/BIBTEX>
 13. Belal IEH, Al-Dosari M (1999) Replacement of Fish Meal with *Salicornia* Meal in Feeds for Nile Tilapia *Oreochromis niloticus*. J World Aquac Soc 30:285–289. <https://doi.org/10.1111/J.1749-7345.1999.TB00877.X>

PROFILES OF ALL EXTRACTS

14. Aziz I, Mujeeb A (2022) Halophytes for phytoremediation of hazardous metal(loid)s: A terse review on metal tolerance, bio-indication and hyperaccumulation. *J Hazard Mater* 424:127309. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JHAZMAT.2021.127309>
15. Ahmadi F, Mohammadkhani N, Servati M (2022) Halophytes play important role in phytoremediation of salt-affected soils in the bed of Urmia Lake, Iran. *Scientific Reports* 2022 12:1 12:1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-16266-4>
16. Yadav S, Mishra A, Jha B (2018) Elevated CO₂ leads to carbon sequestration by modulating C₄ photosynthesis pathway enzyme (PPDK) in *Suaeda monoica* and *S. fruticosa*. *J Photochem Photobiol B* 178:310–315. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JPHOTOBIO.2017.11.022>
17. Belal IEH, Al-Dosari M (1999) Replacement of Fish Meal with *Salicornia* Meal in Feeds for Nile Tilapia *Oreochromis niloticus*. *J World Aquac Soc* 30:285–289. <https://doi.org/10.1111/J.1749-7345.1999.TB00877.X>
18. Chaturvedi T, Torres AI, Stephanopoulos G, et al (2020) Developing Process Designs for Biorefineries—Definitions, Categories, and Unit Operations. *Energies* 2020, Vol 13, Page 1493 13:1493. <https://doi.org/10.3390/EN13061493>
19. Höltinger S, Schmidt J, Schönhart M, Schmid E (2014) A spatially explicit techno-economic assessment of green biorefinery concepts. *Biofuels, Bioproducts and Biorefining* 8:325–341. <https://doi.org/10.1002/BBB.1461>
20. Fredsgaard M, Tchoumtchoua J, Kohnen S, et al (2023) Isolation of Polyphenols from Aqueous Extract of the Halophyte *Salicornia ramosissima*. *Molecules* 2024, Vol 29, Page 220 29:220. <https://doi.org/10.3390/MOLECULES29010220>
21. Hulkko LSS, Rocha RM, Trentin R, et al (2023) Bioactive Extracts from *Salicornia ramosissima* J. Woods Biorefinery as a Source of Ingredients for High-Value Industries. *Plants* 2023, Vol 12, Page 1251 12:1251. <https://doi.org/10.3390/PLANTS12061251>
22. Mariotti F, Tomé D, Mirand P (2008) Converting Nitrogen into Protein—Beyond 6.25 and Jones' Factors. *Crit Rev Food Sci Nutr* 48:177–184. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408390701279749>
23. Krul ES (2019) Calculation of Nitrogen-to-Protein Conversion Factors: A Review with a Focus on Soy Protein. *J Am Oil Chem Soc* 96:339–364. <https://doi.org/10.1002/AOCS.12196>
24. Sluiter A, Hames B, Ruiz R, et al (2006) Determination of Sugars, Byproducts, and Degradation Products in Liquid Fraction Process Samples: Laboratory Analytical Procedure (LAP); Issue Date: 12/08/2006
25. Sluiter A, Hames B, Ruiz R, et al (2008) Determination of Structural Carbohydrates and Lignin in Biomass: Laboratory Analytical Procedure (LAP) (Revised July 2011)

PROFILES OF ALL EXTRACTS

26. Alassali A, Cybulska I, Galvan AR, Thomsen MH (2017) Wet fractionation of the succulent halophyte *Salicornia sinus-persica*, with the aim of low input (water saving) biorefining into bioethanol. *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol* 101:1769–1779. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S00253-016-8049-8/METRICS>
27. Wychen S Van, Ramirez K, Laurens LML (2013) Determination of Total Lipids as Fatty Acid Methyl Esters (FAME) by in situ Transesterification: Laboratory Analytical Procedure (LAP) (Revised)
28. Sluiter A, Ruiz R, Scarlata C, et al (2008) Determination of Extractives in Biomass: Laboratory Analytical Procedure (LAP); Issue Date 7/17/2005
29. Singleton VL, Orthofer R, Lamuela-Raventós RM (1999) Analysis of total phenols and other oxidation substrates and antioxidants by means of folin-ciocalteu reagent. *Methods Enzymol* 299:152–178. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0076-6879\(99\)99017-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0076-6879(99)99017-1)
30. Pirbalouti AG, Siahpoosh A, Setayesh M, Craker L (2014) Antioxidant activity, total phenolic and flavonoid contents of some medicinal and aromatic plants used as herbal teas and condiments in Iran. *J Med Food* 17:1151–1157. <https://doi.org/10.1089/JMF.2013.0057>
31. Li Y-G, Tanner G, Larkin P (1996) The DMACA-HC1 Protocol and the Threshold Proanthocyanidin Content for Bloat Safety in Forage Legumes. *J Sci Food Agric* 70:89–101. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1097-0010\(199601\)70:1](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1097-0010(199601)70:1)
32. Benzie IFF, Strain JJ (1996) The ferric reducing ability of plasma (FRAP) as a measure of “antioxidant power”: The FRAP assay. *Analytical Biochemistry* 239:70–76. <https://doi.org/10.1006/abio.1996.0292>
33. Sharma OP, Bhat TK (2009) DPPH antioxidant assay revisited. *Food Chemistry* 113:1202–1205. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2008.08.008>
34. Xiao Z, Storms R, Tsang A (2006) A quantitative starch-iodine method for measuring alpha-amylase and glucoamylase activities. *Anal Biochem* 351:146–148. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.AB.2006.01.036>
35. Custódio L, Patarra J, Alberício F, et al (2015) Phenolic composition, antioxidant potential and in vitro inhibitory activity of leaves and acorns of *Quercus suber* on key enzymes relevant for hyperglycemia and Alzheimer’s disease. *Ind Crops Prod* 64:45–51. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.INDCROP.2014.11.001>
36. McDougall GJ, Kulkarni NN, Stewart D (2009) Berry polyphenols inhibit pancreatic lipase activity in vitro. *Food Chem* 115:193–199. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FOODCHEM.2008.11.093>
37. Trentin R, Custódio L, Rodrigues MJ, et al (2020) Exploring *Ulva australis* Areschoug for possible biotechnological applications: In vitro antioxidant and enzymatic inhibitory

PROFILES OF ALL EXTRACTS

- properties, and fatty acids contents. *Algal Res* 50:101980. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ALGAL.2020.101980>
38. Ellman GL, Courtney KD, Andres V, Featherstone RM (1961) A new and rapid colorimetric determination of acetylcholinesterase activity. *Biochem Pharmacol* 7:. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0006-2952\(61\)90145-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0006-2952(61)90145-9)
39. Hulkko LSS, Chaturvedi T, Custódio L, Thomsen MH (2023) Harnessing the Value of *Tripolium pannonicum* and *Crithmum maritimum* Halophyte Biomass through Integrated Green Biorefinery. *Marine Drugs* 2023, Vol 21, Page 380 21:380. <https://doi.org/10.3390/MD21070380>
40. Rodrigues MJ, Gangadhar KN, Vizetto-Duarte C, et al (2014) Maritime Halophyte Species from Southern Portugal as Sources of Bioactive Molecules. *Marine Drugs* 2014, Vol 12, Pages 2228-2244 12:2228–2244. <https://doi.org/10.3390/MD12042228>
41. Carr I, Glencross B, Santigosa E (2023) The importance of essential fatty acids and their ratios in aquafeeds to enhance salmonid production, welfare, and human health. *Frontiers in Animal Science* 4:1147081. <https://doi.org/10.3389/FANIM.2023.1147081/BIBTEX>
42. Custodio L, Garcia-Caparros P, Pereira CG, Castelo-Branco P (2022) Halophyte Plants as Potential Sources of Anticancer Agents: A Comprehensive Review. *Pharmaceutics* 14:. <https://doi.org/10.3390/PHARMACEUTICS14112406>
43. Heleno SA, Martins A, Queiroz MJRP, Ferreira ICFR (2015) Bioactivity of phenolic acids: metabolites versus parent compounds: a review. *Food Chem* 173:501–513. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FOODCHEM.2014.10.057>
44. Yang WS, Jeong D, Yi YS, et al (2013) IRAK1/4-targeted anti-inflammatory action of caffeic acid. *Mediators Inflamm* 2013:. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2013/518183>
45. Sólyom K, Solá R, Cocero MJ, Mato RB (2014) Thermal degradation of grape marc polyphenols. *Food Chem* 159:361–366. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FOODCHEM.2014.03.021>

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Document information

Grant no	101084651	Acronym	IGNITION
Full title	Improving green innovation for the blue revolution		
Project website	www.ignition-project.eu		

Deliverable	Nº	3.2	Title	Complete chemical composition and bioactivity profiles of all extracts
Work Package	Nº	3	Title	Functional feeds
Work Package Leader	Mette Hedegaard Thomsen			
Work Participants	Stanislav Rudnyckyj			

Lead Beneficiary	Aalborg University
Authors	Stanislav Rudnyckyj
Reviewers	Mette Hedegaard Thomsen, Tânia Pereira, Benjamin Costas, Marina Machado and Lourenço Ramos-Pinto

Due date of deliverable	31 May 2024
Submission date	27 May 2024
Dissemination level	Public
Type of deliverable	Report

Version Log			
Issue Date	Revision Nº	Author	Change
10 May 2024	0.1	Stanislav Rudnyckyj	First version
16 May 2024	0.2	Mette Hedegaard Thomsen	Reviewed by
24 May 2024	0.3	Tânia Pereira	Reviewed by
28 May 2024	0.4	Stanislav Rudnyckyj	Reviewed by
30 May 2024	0.5	Tânia Pereira & Benjamin Costas	Reviewed by
31 May 2024	1.0	Stanislav Rudnyckyj	Accepted version
29 June 2024		Martin Syvret, Snjezana Zrncic and German Valcarcel-Resalt	Project review
12 July 2024	1.1	Stanislav Rudnyckyj	Updated according to suggestions
24 July 2024	1.2	Tânia Pereira, Lourenço Pinto, Marina Machado and Benjamin Costas	Reviewed by

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26 July 2024	2.0		Submitted version
5 August 2024		Martin Syvret, Snjezana Zrncic and German Valcarcel-Resalt	Deliverable evaluation comments
15 August 2024	2.1	Tânia Pereira	Corrections
19 August 2024	3.0	Stanislav Rudnyckyj	Submitted version

2024